

On Bayesian inference in pulsar timing arrays: identifiability and choice of the priors

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Abstract

Pulsar Timing Arrays (PTAs) represent one of the most active and rapidly evolving research areas in contemporary astrophysics. PTAs use pulsar observations to search for gravitational waves, relying on accurate statistical models of pulsar timing data. In this work, we revisit the bias problem reported in both Bayesian and frequentist analyses and identify the structural features of the statistical models that give rise to these effects. We show that it originates from an underlying identifiability issue in commonly used linear Gaussian models. We outline and discuss different possible remedies to the non-identifiability. For instance, one possible approach is the use of hierarchical priors, which can alleviate non-identifiability but at the cost of making the inference strongly prior-dependent: the choice of the prior effectively selects one specific set of parameters among infinitely many equivalent solutions. Hence, in these non-identifiable models, the resulting inference outputs along the non-identifiable directions are effectively determined by the choice of the prior, rather than by the data themselves (becoming completely prior-driven). Moreover, we also highlight the limitations of the use of diffuse and improper priors in Bayesian model selection, as they can distort Bayes factors and compromise the robustness of gravitational-wave detection analyses. Finally, we give an overview of best practice for prior choice in model selection and suggest possible remedies to the limitations of linear PTA models reported in literature.

Keywords: Pulsar timing arrays (PTAs); Bayesian inference; Linear Gaussian models; identifiability; Prior densities.

1 Introduction

Pulsars are highly magnetised rotating neutron stars that emit beams of electromagnetic radiation from their poles, which are observed from the Earth as periodic pulses when the observer is aligned with their direction of emission. They have long been a focus of astrophysical research due to their role as precise cosmic clocks and probes of fundamental physics [3, 10, 26]. Interference with such precise periods can in fact reveal many cosmological and astrophysical phenomena.

Accurate modelling and analysis of pulsar signals are essential for applications, mainly tests of general relativity via gravitational-wave detection with pulsar timing arrays. Pulsar timing arrays (PTAs) use an array of millisecond pulsars to search for gravitational waves, by observing delays in the time of pulse arrival. From a statistical point of view, Gaussian linear models (GLMs) offer a powerful and interpretable framework for analysing pulsar signals [6, 24, 28, 30]. GLMs easily extend to the hierarchical Bayesian formulations which seem the most suitable framework: prior distributions can encode astrophysical knowledge (e.g., spin-down rates, dispersion measures) or regularisation assumptions (e.g., smoothness of pulse profiles) [22].

However, several authors have highlighted “posterior bias” issues [12, 15, 31, 35]. Posterior bias means that the reported parameter estimates (and uncertainties) are systematically shifted/biased away from the truth because of model misspecification or prior influence. This is a critical issue in PTAs, since even small biases can mimic or hide the signatures of gravitational waves, leading to potential false positive statistics. For instance, the authors in [12] have discussed how pulsar timing analyses can produce biased posteriors for gravitational-wave background parameters if noise models are oversimplified. In [35, 15], the authors have shown posterior biases in analyses of pulsar noise properties, particularly when disentangling intrinsic pulsar red noise from interstellar medium effects. Furthermore, several other studies have used the same models and prior densities [1, 2].

In this work, we aim to clarify several aspects that may have led to confusion in the literature, as well as to elucidate the underlying causes of the posterior bias issue and other possibly misleading results in model selection. The PTA inference problem is inherently challenging, since the relevant physical information sought by researchers is encoded within the hyper-parameters of the selected prior, which must be specified by the researchers themselves. In similar scenarios, an empirical Bayes or related methods are required to infer the hyper-parameters of the prior density. To be more specific, given a vector of parameters defining the delays in the pulse time of arrival (TOA) \mathbf{b} , a Gaussian prior with zero mean and covariance matrix Σ_b is often assumed, i.e., $\mathbf{b} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b}|\mathbf{0}, \Sigma_b)$. These parameters include several astrophysical values and the Fourier coefficients of the decomposition of the frequency-dependent red noise (that is considered in this application). The main quantity of interest in PTA inference is the prior-covariance matrix Σ_b , which contains information on physically relevant parameters, such as (a) the intrinsic red noise, (b) the (electromagnetic) dispersion measure and (c) gravitational waves. Note that this goal requires information on the variability of the vector \mathbf{b} . We have recognised the presence of an underlying identifiability issue, which we argue constitutes the fundamental cause of the bias observed in the resulting estimators. Thus, in the following, we provide a detailed discussion of the identifiability properties of two classes of linear Gaussian models, which appear to be among the most frequently employed frameworks in the pulsar literature [17, 31]. Building on this analysis, we subsequently present and examine the principal strategies that have been proposed as potential remedies to address this identifiability problem. We also empirically analyse the more sophisticated likelihood function implemented in the state-of-the-art Python package `enterprise` [9, 10, 29], verifying the presence of a possible non-identifiability issue.

Moreover, given that the primary objective of PTA analyses is the detection of gravitational

waves, a substantial body of work in the literature has focused on the development of Bayesian hypothesis testing frameworks, and some of them using (hypothetically) uninformative priors [8, 14, 18, 32]. Within this context, many authors formulate and compare two competing models: the first explicitly incorporating a gravitational-wave signal, and the second serving as a null model that accounts solely for noise contributions. This procedure entails the computation of Bayes factors and, consequently, of the corresponding marginal likelihoods [27, 16, 33, 20, 22]. In this work, we further highlight some issues that may arise when diffuse (uninformative) and improper priors are employed for the purpose of model selection, underscoring the potential implications such choices may have on the validity and robustness of the resulting inference [4, 19, 23, 25]. We summarise below the key messages and practical implications that we believe represent the central takeaways of this study:

- The pulsar models employed in many works of the literature are fundamentally prone to non-identifiability, unless strong structural assumptions are imposed, meaning that infinitely many combinations of the parameters yield the same value of the likelihood function. The use of hierarchical priors over the model parameters is one possible remedy for non-identifiability. However, this comes at the cost of selecting one specific parameter combination among infinitely many equivalent possibilities. Consequently, the choice of hierarchical priors can very strongly influence the solution, making the inference largely prior-driven.
- The use of vague or diffuse priors, although often regarded as uninformative in the context of parameter estimation, can be highly informative in model selection settings. Furthermore, improper priors are generally unsuitable for model comparison, since the corresponding marginal likelihoods are not well defined and can only be evaluated up to an arbitrary normalizing constant.

Throughout this paper, we examine the PTA models most commonly adopted in literature and discuss their identifiability limitations in Section 2; we address such limitations, by proposing practical remedies to them in Section 3; we extend our discussion to the state-of-the-art `enterprise` modeling software and its likelihood function in Section 4; finally, we discuss the role of prior choice in model selection and why improper priors should never be adopted in the given context in Section 5.

2 Employed models and identifiability

In this Section, we describe the main models used in the literature to perform inference in PTAs [17, 31], and discuss their identifiability. First, we recall the definition of identifiability.

Identifiability. Let us say that a model depends on the choice of several parameters. If different parameter values lead to different distributions of the observed data $\{\mathbf{y}_n\}$, then the model is identifiable. Otherwise, the model is said to be non-identifiable, if there exist different parameter values that yield exactly the same distribution for $\{\mathbf{y}_n\}$. For this reason, we will focus mainly on the marginal distribution of the data. In other words, a model is said to be identifiable if, given an infinite number of observations, the true values of its parameters can be uniquely determined. In this context, the data represent the TOA delays of a single pulsar.

2.1 Model A: individual latent variables

We assume the following observation model (see, e.g., [31]),

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{y}_n = \mathbf{s}_n + \mathbf{v}_n \\ \quad = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n + \mathbf{v}_n, \\ \mathbf{b}_n \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b}|\boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b), \\ \mathbf{v}_n \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{v}|\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v), \end{cases} \quad n = 1, \dots, N, \quad (1)$$

where we have the observed vector $\mathbf{y}_n = [y_{n,1}, \dots, y_{n,M}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 1}$, where we have the unknown vectors $\mathbf{b}_n = [b_{n,1}, \dots, b_{n,K}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times 1}$, $\mathbf{v}_n \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 1}$ and the matrix $\mathbf{T} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times K}$. Here, the observations \mathbf{y}_n are the time residuals of the beam pulses from the pulsars in the array; \mathbf{b}_n is usually modelled as a vector comprising the parameters of the linearised physical model of the pulsars and the Fourier coefficients of the frequency-dependent processes; \mathbf{v}_n are realisations of an instrumental Gaussian noise. In the PTA setting, N is the number of observed residuals, M is the number of pulsars in the array, and K is the number of parameters contributing to the time delays. The covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b$ has size $K \times K$, whereas $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v$ has size $M \times M$. In this work, we focus on the case $K \leq M$. Hence, the vector \mathbf{v}_n is a Gaussian noise perturbation with zero mean and $M \times M$ covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v$. We assume a Gaussian prior density over \mathbf{b}_n , with a $K \times 1$ vector mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}_b$ and a $K \times K$ covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b$. Since $\mathbf{s}_n = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 1}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{s}_n &\sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{s}|\boldsymbol{\mu}_s, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s) \\ &\sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{s}|\mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

i.e., $\boldsymbol{\mu}_s = \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\mu}_b$, and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s = \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top$. Hence, we assume known and observed:

- the $M \times K$ matrix \mathbf{T} ,
- \mathbf{y}_n , for all $n = 1, \dots, N$,

and we would like to estimate/approximate:

- \mathbf{b}_n , $n = 1, \dots, N$,
- the parameter of the prior $\boldsymbol{\mu}_b$, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b$, and the covariance matrix of the noise $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v$.

Figure 1 gives a graphical representation of Model A. The vector \mathbf{b}_n 's are generated independently from the prior $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b}|\boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b)$. It is important to note that the vector \mathbf{b}_n is related with only one observed vector, namely \mathbf{y}_n . It is also worth emphasising that, in pulsar analyses, the matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b$ embodies crucial physical information.

2.2 Identifiability of Model A

Given the model above, the main expressions and assumptions to take into account are:

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}_n] = \boldsymbol{\mu}_y = \boldsymbol{\mu}_s = \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Cov}[\mathbf{y}_n] = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_y = \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v, \quad (4)$$

Figure 1: Graphical representation of Model A. Each vector \mathbf{y}_i provides information only on \mathbf{b}_i .

where we have used $\Sigma_s = \mathbf{T}\Sigma_b\mathbf{T}^\top$. All identifiability statements are related to the marginal distribution of \mathbf{y}_n .

Marginal density of a single observation \mathbf{y}_n . Since the marginal distribution of \mathbf{y}_n is Gaussian (as shown Section A.2), it is completely defined with the expressions above. Considering the prior $\mathbf{b}_n \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b}|\boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b)$, we can also obtain the marginal distribution of a single observation \mathbf{y}_n , integrating out \mathbf{b}_n . This is also Gaussian,

$$\begin{aligned} p(\mathbf{y}_n | \boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) &= \int \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_n | \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b}_n | \boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b) d\mathbf{b}_n, \\ &= \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_n | \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v), \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Fixing \mathbf{y}_n , the expression above is also the *marginal likelihood* for a single observation. Since we observe $\{\mathbf{y}_n\}_{n=1}^N$, and we can always compute the estimators

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_y = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbf{y}_n, \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_y = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (\mathbf{y}_n - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_y)(\mathbf{y}_n - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_y)^\top, \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_y$ is an estimator of $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{y}_n] = \boldsymbol{\mu}_s = \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\mu}_b$, and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_y$ is an estimator of the covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_y$.

Model A is non-identifiable. In principle, the model seems identifiable. Clearly, we can estimate $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_y = \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v$. The problem is to univocally identify the two contributions $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v$. Seemingly, since each \mathbf{y}_i provides information about one \mathbf{b}_i , we could obtain estimators $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i$ (e.g., by least squares). Theoretically, there are two possible procedures:

- P1.** We could estimate the variability of the \mathbf{b}_i 's by computing the empirical covariance $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_b$ of the $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i$, so we would be able to separate the contributions of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v$, obtaining

$\widehat{\Sigma}_v = \widehat{\Sigma}_y - \mathbf{T}\widehat{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top$. However, we will show below that the estimator $\widehat{\Sigma}_b$ is *biased* and is *non-consistent* as $N \rightarrow \infty$. See Section 2.2.1.

P2. An alternative is to estimate the residuals $\widehat{\mathbf{v}}_n = \mathbf{y}_n - \mathbf{T}\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n$ and compute the empirical covariance matrix of the noise $\widehat{\Sigma}_v = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \widehat{\mathbf{v}}_i \widehat{\mathbf{v}}_i^\top$. However, it is possible to show that this matrix $\widehat{\Sigma}_v$ is only positive *semi-definite* since it has at least one null eigenvalue. Moreover, $\widehat{\Sigma}_v$ is a biased and non-consistent estimator of Σ_v .

In any case, we can only estimate the sum $\Sigma_y = \mathbf{T}\Sigma_b\mathbf{T}^\top + \Sigma_v$; we cannot uniquely separate Σ_b and Σ_v . Thus, different pairs (Σ_b, Σ_v) can produce the same marginal distribution for \mathbf{y}_n . As a result, there are infinitely many parameter configurations consistent with the observed distribution of \mathbf{y}_n , and any optimisation algorithm (including EM) will converge to one of these multiple maxima, depending on its initialisation.

2.2.1 Discussing the possible (wrong) solution P1

The statement above can be surprising since we can actually estimate each \mathbf{b}_n by least squares (LS) and, as a consequence, also estimate Σ_b . Let us assume $K \leq M$, $N > 1$, and $\text{rank}(\mathbf{T}) = K$, then the $K \times K$ square matrix $\mathbf{T}^\top\mathbf{T}$ is invertible, which makes possible to apply LS estimators, i.e.,

$$\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{LS})} = (\mathbf{T}^\top\mathbf{T})^{-1}\mathbf{T}^\top\mathbf{y}_n, \quad n = 1, \dots, N. \quad (8)$$

Moreover since, by assumption, the vectors \mathbf{b}_n are distributed according to the same Gaussian distribution, we could estimate

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_b &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{LS})} \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (\mathbf{T}^\top\mathbf{T})^{-1}\mathbf{T}^\top\mathbf{y}_n \\ &= (\mathbf{T}^\top\mathbf{T})^{-1}\mathbf{T}^\top \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbf{y}_n \right] \\ &= (\mathbf{T}^\top\mathbf{T})^{-1}\mathbf{T}^\top\widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_y, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where, in the last step, we have replaced $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_y = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbf{y}_n$ in Eq. (6). Furthermore, we can also estimate

$$\widehat{\Sigma}_b = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{LS})} - \widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_b \right) \left(\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{LS})} - \widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_b \right)^\top, \quad (10)$$

If \mathbf{T} is full rank, these estimators are also unique. Finally, the covariance noise could be estimated via

$$\widehat{\Sigma}_v = \widehat{\Sigma}_y - \mathbf{T}\widehat{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top. \quad (11)$$

The model A would be identifiable, using the procedure above. *Why does it fail in practice?*

Issue in P1. The previous procedure fails since the LS estimates $\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n$ are noisy variables and, as a consequence, their empirical covariance reflects not only the true latent covariance $\widehat{\Sigma}_b$ but also an additional contribution arising from the noise perturbation \mathbf{v}_n (that induces additional variability in the estimates $\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n$). Thus, the procedure above provides a *biased* estimator of Σ_b .

Derivation of the bias. Consider $\mathbf{y}_n = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n + \mathbf{v}_n$ and the LS estimator of \mathbf{b}_n ,

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{LS})} &= (\mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{T})^{-1} \mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{y}_n \\ &= (\mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{T})^{-1} \mathbf{T}^\top (\mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n + \mathbf{v}_n) \\ &= \mathbf{b}_n + (\mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{T})^{-1} \mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{v}_n,\end{aligned}\tag{12}$$

hence $\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{LS})}$ equals the true latent \mathbf{b}_n plus an error term coming from the projected noise. Note that $\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{LS})}] = \mathbf{b}_n$ since $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{v}_n] = \mathbf{0}$, hence the estimates of \mathbf{b}_n are unbiased. However, computing the empirical covariance,

$$\widehat{\Sigma}_b = \Sigma_b + (\mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{T})^{-1} \mathbf{T}^\top \Sigma_v \mathbf{T} (\mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{T})^{-1}\tag{13}$$

$$= \Sigma_b + \Sigma_{\text{bias}}\tag{14}$$

we have a bias since $\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\Sigma}_b] \neq \Sigma_b$. The bias term Σ_{bias} is a positive-semidefinite matrix determined by \mathbf{T} and Σ_v . Moreover, and even more important, the empirical covariance $\widehat{\Sigma}_b$ is not a consistent estimator of Σ_b unless that extra term is zero, i.e., $\Sigma_v = \mathbf{0}$ (or unless we are able to correct/subtract it).

2.2.2 Discussing the possible (wrong) solution P2

Assuming $\text{rank}(\mathbf{T}) = K$ and recalling $\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{LS})} = (\mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{T})^{-1} \mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{y}_n$, we can estimate the residuals $\widehat{\mathbf{v}}_n = \mathbf{y}_n - \mathbf{T}\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n$ and compute the empirical covariance matrix of the noise

$$\widehat{\Sigma}_v = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \widehat{\mathbf{v}}_n \widehat{\mathbf{v}}_n^\top.$$

Issue in P2. However, we can observe that

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{\mathbf{v}}_n &= \mathbf{y}_n - \mathbf{T}\widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n \\ &= \mathbf{y}_n - \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{T})^{-1} \mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{y}_n \\ &= (\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P})\mathbf{y}_n \\ &= (\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P})(\mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n + \mathbf{v}_n) \\ &= (\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P})\mathbf{v}_n,\end{aligned}$$

where we have set $\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{T})^{-1} \mathbf{T}^\top$ and \mathbf{I}_M is the $M \times M$ identity matrix and it is possible to prove $(\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P})\mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n = \mathbf{0}$. We can replace the expression obtained above, $\widehat{\mathbf{v}}_n = (\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P})\mathbf{v}_n$, into

the empirical covariance estimation

$$\widehat{\Sigma}_v = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \widehat{\mathbf{v}}_n \widehat{\mathbf{v}}_n^\top \quad (15)$$

$$= (\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P}) \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbf{v}_n \mathbf{v}_n^\top \right] (\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P})^\top \quad (16)$$

$$= (\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P}) \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbf{v}_n \mathbf{v}_n^\top \right] (\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P}), \quad (17)$$

where in the last expression we have used $\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{P}^\top$ (and $\mathbf{I}_M = \mathbf{I}_M^\top$ clearly). Applying the expectation of both sides, we obtain

$$\Sigma_r = \mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\Sigma}_v \right] = (\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P}) \Sigma_v (\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P}). \quad (18)$$

Thus, $\widehat{\Sigma}_v$ is an estimator of $(\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P}) \Sigma_v (\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P})$, instead of Σ_v itself. Then, $\widehat{\Sigma}_v$ is biased and not consistent. Moreover, the expression above explains the presence of some zero eigenvalue(s). Indeed, we have that $\text{rank}(\mathbf{P}) = K$ if $\text{rank}(\mathbf{T}) = K$ and $\text{rank}(\mathbf{I}_M) = M$ (since it is an identity matrix), hence $\text{rank}(\mathbf{I}_M - \mathbf{P}) = M - K$. Therefore, we can assert that Σ_r has rank at most $M - K$. Therefore Σ_r has at least K zero eigenvalues (if Σ_v is full rank then $\text{rank}(\Sigma_r) = M - K$ exactly). In Appendix A we show more precise (Bayesian) estimators. However, their use does not fix the identifiability issue.

2.3 Model B: single common latent variable

We describe here another possible model that is used in the pulsar-timing literature (see, e.g., [17]). Let us assume that $\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}$ does not depend on the sub-index n , i.e.,

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{y}_n = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{v}_n, \\ \mathbf{b} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b} | \boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \Sigma_b), \\ \mathbf{v}_n \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{v} | \mathbf{0}, \Sigma_v), \end{cases} \quad n = 1, \dots, N, \quad (19)$$

Figure 2 depicts a graphical representation of the model above. In this model, the vectors of \mathbf{y}_n are linked with only *one sample* of the vector \mathbf{b} . All the vectors \mathbf{y}_n provide information on \mathbf{b} . Thus, having many samples \mathbf{y}_n gives us a more accurate estimation of the unique vector \mathbf{b} . However, we have only one sample of \mathbf{b} and the estimation of its variability and internal covariances becomes impossible, leading to an identifiability problem. More specifically, we have:

$$\widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_y = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{y}_i \xrightarrow{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}, \quad (20)$$

$$\widehat{\Sigma}_y = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (\mathbf{y}_n - \widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_y) (\mathbf{y}_n - \widehat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_y)^\top \xrightarrow{N \rightarrow \infty} \Sigma_v, \quad (21)$$

Figure 2: Graphical representation of Model B. All the vectors \mathbf{y}_i provide information regarding the unique vector \mathbf{b} .

hence in this case we can estimate Σ_v but we have no information about Σ_b .

Model B is non-identifiable. The vector \mathbf{b} is shared across all observed data \mathbf{y}_i ; with only a single realisation of \mathbf{b} , we obtain no information about Σ_b (which is effectively “invisible” with just one sample of \mathbf{b}). Unlike in Model A, we can estimate the covariance of the noise Σ_v using the empirical covariance of the data $\hat{\Sigma}_y$, but still we are not able to estimate Σ_b (since we have a unique sample of \mathbf{b}). As a final remark, we note that assuming the prior mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}_b$ to be known may help recover the diagonal elements of Σ_b ; however, the remaining entries would still pose a challenge. See also the illustrative example in Appendix B for theoretical formulas of an interesting special case.

3 Strategies for addressing non-identifiability

In this section, we outline four main strategies for addressing non-identifiability:

1. knowing Σ_b and/or Σ_v ;
2. imposing additional structure on Σ_b and Σ_v ;
3. introducing priors on Σ_b and Σ_v ;
4. exploiting additional information, for example by having more realisations for each \mathbf{b}_n .

(i) **Knowing Σ_b and/or Σ_v .** If one of the matrices Σ_b or Σ_v is known (or has been reliably estimated in a previous step), then the other can be estimated by the relationship below,

$$\mathbf{T}\hat{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top = \hat{\Sigma}_y - \Sigma_v, \quad \text{or} \quad \hat{\Sigma}_v = \hat{\Sigma}_y - \mathbf{T}\Sigma_b\mathbf{T}^\top.$$

(ii) **Impose structure to Σ_b and Σ_v .** In order to identify Σ_b and Σ_v , it is necessary to reduce

the number of free parameters by imposing additional structure or constraints. For instance, one could assume isotropic noise, $\Sigma_v = \sigma_v^2 \mathbf{I}_M$ and/or $\Sigma_b = \sigma_b^2 \mathbf{I}_K$ (hence, depending only on two scalar values σ_v^2, σ_b^2). In this way, the degrees of freedom are substantially reduced and, under suitable regularity conditions, both matrices can be uniquely identified. More generally, more parametric/structured covariances could solve the identifiability issue: if Σ_b and/or Σ_v are restricted to a parametric family with few parameters (diagonal or band matrix, low-rank, etc.), then the parameters can often be estimated uniquely. This is also what seems to happen in the model employed Python library `enterprise` [9, 10, 17, 31, 29] (see related Section below).

(iii) Assuming priors to Σ_b and Σ_v . The use of priors on the covariance matrices allows the identifiability, since the introduction of the prior densities selects a specific solution (i.e., one pair of covariance matrices) among the infinitely many admissible pairs (Σ_b, Σ_v) . It is therefore important to emphasise that the choice of the priors strongly determines the solution, rendering the inference largely prior-driven. This issue has been partially highlighted in the literature [31].

(iv) More realisations. Suppose we consider a model of the form

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{y}_n^{(r)} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n + \mathbf{v}_n^{(r)}, \\ \mathbf{b}_n \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b}|\boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \Sigma_b), \\ \mathbf{v}_n^{(r)} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{v}|\mathbf{0}, \Sigma_v), \end{cases} \quad n = 1, \dots, N, \quad r = 1, \dots, R, \quad (22)$$

where we have R different observations for each \mathbf{b}_n . In this case, we can separate the contributions of Σ_b and Σ_v . Indeed, with

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}}_n = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R \mathbf{y}_n^{(r)}, \quad \hat{\Sigma}_v = \frac{1}{NR} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{r=1}^R (\mathbf{y}_n^{(r)} - \bar{\mathbf{y}}_n) (\mathbf{y}_n^{(r)} - \bar{\mathbf{y}}_n)^\top \approx \Sigma_v, \quad (23)$$

we can estimate Σ_v as in Model B, and

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}}^{(r)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbf{y}_n^{(r)}, \quad (24)$$

$$\hat{\Sigma}_y = \frac{1}{NR} \sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{n=1}^N (\mathbf{y}_n^{(r)} - \bar{\mathbf{y}}^{(r)}) (\mathbf{y}_n^{(r)} - \bar{\mathbf{y}}^{(r)})^\top \approx \Sigma_y = \mathbf{T}\Sigma_b\mathbf{T}^\top + \Sigma_v \quad (25)$$

Hence, we can also obtain

$$\mathbf{T}\Sigma_b\mathbf{T}^\top \approx \hat{\Sigma}_y - \hat{\Sigma}_v, \quad (26)$$

and

$$\hat{\Sigma}_b = \mathbf{T}_{\text{pinv}} \left(\hat{\Sigma}_y - \hat{\Sigma}_v \right) \mathbf{T}_{\text{pinv}}^\top, \quad (27)$$

where $\mathbf{T}_{\text{pinv}} = (\mathbf{T}^\top \mathbf{T})^{-1} \mathbf{T}^\top$. This procedure can be employed for obtaining good starting estimates and use them in more sophisticated computational algorithms as initialization. Figure 3 represents the model above. We can observe that this model shares and combines properties of Model A and Model B.

Figure 3: Graphical representation of $\mathbf{y}_n^{(r)} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n + \mathbf{v}_n^{(r)}$.

4 Analysis of the likelihood in the enterprise library

In this Section, we analyse the likelihood function implemented in the Python library `enterprise` [9], that is considered the state-of-the-art code in PTA analysis [10, 17, 31, 29]. Based on the available documentation and several references, the exact analytical form of the likelihood function does not appear to be properly documented (at least, not all the steps and details). The likelihood structure seems sufficiently sophisticated that we treat it as effectively intractable for analytical manipulation. By the papers citing `enterprise`, we understand that the employed likelihood is related to Models A and B described earlier (see, e.g., [10, 13, 17, 11, 29, 31]). However, a close examination of the code reveals also that multiple pre-processing, intermediate, and supplementary modelling steps are involved in the likelihood construction. Hence, the `enterprise` framework employs a more complex and structured model than Models A and B (its effective parametrisation involves four main parameters). Nevertheless, issues related to non-identifiability still appear, as we illustrate in this Section.

We focus on the data (around 10^3) related to one pulsar, denoted as J0030 + 0451. To the best of our knowledge, after certain marginalisation steps (whose details could be more clearly documented), the inference in `enterprise` focuses on four parameters, $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = [\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3, \theta_4]$, where $\theta_1 = \gamma_{dm}$ is the spectral index of the electromagnetic dispersion, $\theta_2 = \gamma_{rn}$ is the spectral index of the intrinsic red noise, $\theta_3 = \log_{10} A_{dm}$ is the amplitude parameter of the electromagnetic dispersion, $\theta_4 = \log_{10} A_{rn}$ is the amplitude parameter of the intrinsic red noise. The dispersion measure is due to the interaction between radio waves and the interstellar medium, while the red-noise is due to mainly intrinsic pulsar phenomena like spin-noise. Moreover, we consider several samples drawn from the corresponding posterior using the Python implementation `NESSAI` [34], which is based on an advanced nested-sampling scheme that also generates samples from the posterior. For a complete description of classical nested sampling (which only approximates the marginal likelihood), see the arXiv version of [20]. For each such posterior sample, we then compute the likelihood function. Then, we sort in decreasing order of the likelihood evaluations and the corresponding samples.

Case	θ_1	θ_2	log-likelihood
highest log-likelihood	2.0496	2.8462	17867.97
min θ_1 (top 500)	0.9397	2.9369	17858.05
min θ_2 (top 500)	2.3934	2.0157	17858.01
max θ_1 (top 500)	3.6761	3.2607	17856.81
max θ_2 (top 500)	1.9572	5.6989	17856.79
lowest log-likelihood (top 500)	2.4085	4.0517	17855.73

Table 1: Representative values of θ_1 , θ_2 and the log-likelihood for the `enterprise` analysis. The table shows six cases: the sample with the highest log-likelihood sample, the samples with minimum and maximum values of θ_1 and θ_2 among the top 500 samples ranked by likelihood, and the sample with the lowest log-likelihood value within that set.

In Figure 4, we show the first 500 values of the components θ_1 and θ_2 , ordered from the pair with the highest likelihood to the pair with the lowest, for ease of visualisation. In the bottom plot, we can observe the corresponding likelihood values (that are sorted in decreasing order, to correspond to the pair above). In Figure 4, it can be observed that distinct parameter pairs $\{\theta_1, \theta_2\}$ produce nearly identical likelihood values, with a variation of about 12.2 units in log-likelihood from about 17856 to 17868 (which corresponds to less than 0.07% relative change on a baseline value of about $1.8 \cdot 10^4$) from the highest to the lowest values. Table 1 provides different examples of pairs and their corresponding likelihood values. Substantial variation can be observed among the parameter pairs, while the corresponding log-likelihood values vary only within a relatively narrow band. This indicates a broad ridge in parameter space, where quite different (θ_1, θ_2) combinations yield similarly high likelihood, rather than a sharply peaked optimum. Such a broad high-likelihood ridge is consistent with the presence of a non-identifiability or near-degeneracy between these parameters. Hence, it appears that, at least for this pulsar and this specific model configuration, the more complex likelihood implemented in `enterprise` (with its associated “marginalisations”) does not fully remove the underlying degeneracy.

5 On the role of prior choice in model selection

In the linear Gaussian models considered above, the likelihood can be non-identifiable, in the sense that infinitely many combinations of (Σ_b, Σ_v) lead to the same marginal distribution of the data. Introducing prior densities over the parameters resolves this formal non-identifiability by selecting a particular region of the parameter space, but it also implies that posterior and model comparison results can be strongly influenced by the chosen priors.

In PTA applications, Bayesian model selection is routinely used to compare models that include a gravitational-wave background with models that contain only independent pulsar noises [14, 18, 32, 31]. In this context, it is therefore important to understand how prior choices affect the marginal likelihood and the associated Bayes factors [16, 20, 24].

To clarify the discussion, let us define a vector θ that collects all the unknown quantities we wish to infer: all the components of \mathbf{b}_n for $n = 1, \dots, N$, together with all the entries of Σ_b and Σ_v ,

Figure 4: We show the two components: $\theta_1 = \gamma_{dm}$ and $\theta_2 = \gamma_{rn}$ of samples supposedly drawn from the posterior, with greatest values of the likelihood, for the pulsar J0030+0451. We depict them in decreasing order of the likelihood evaluations. The first pair of values corresponds to the highest likelihood value, and the last pair corresponds to the smallest likelihood value. We note that quite different pairs of parameters $\{\theta_1, \theta_2\}$ yield very similar likelihood values: between the highest and lowest values, the decrease in log-likelihood is only about 0.07%.

including the hyper-parameters θ^e . For simplicity, we slightly abuse set notation and write

$$\theta := \{ \{ \mathbf{b}_n \}_{n=1}^N, \Sigma_b, \Sigma_v \}, \quad \theta \in \Theta. \quad (28)$$

In cases when the coefficients $\{ \mathbf{b}_n \}_{n=1}^N$ can be marginalised, we have a simpler scenario:

$$\theta := \{ \Sigma_b, \Sigma_v \}, \quad \theta \in \Theta. \quad (29)$$

However, simplified scenarios are possible: for instance, in the setting of `enterprise` analysed above, $\theta = \tilde{\theta}$, i.e. only contains parameters contained in the covariance matrices. In the following Sections, for the sake of clarity, we also use a simplified notation:

- $g(\theta)$: prior density (hence, including the prior densities on $\tilde{\theta}$ parameters, the ones we have control in `enterprise`);

- $\ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})$: complete likelihood density (e.g., in Models A and B, the vector \mathbf{y} here would represent $\mathbf{y}_{1:N}$);
- $\bar{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{y})$: the corresponding posterior distribution.

5.1 Advice 1: diffuse priors are informative for model selection

If the support Θ is unbounded, one could employ a so-called *vague* prior density (a.k.a., *diffuse*, *flat*), i.e., a density with probability mass spread in all the state space (for instance, a Gaussian with a very high variance). Whereas for the inference on the vector of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ these priors tend to be uninformative, they are actually very informative for model selection [7, 19, 22, 23]. To show this point, we use an illustrative example. Let us assume a likelihood function that is integrable in Θ , i.e., $S = \int_{\Theta} \ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta} < \infty$. Note that S is the hyper-volume encased by the likelihood function [23, 19]. Then, we consider a uniform and proper prior defined on the set B , i.e.,

$$g(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{1}{|B|}\mathbf{1}_B(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \quad (30)$$

where $|B|$ is the volume of B . Therefore, the posterior pdf can be written as

$$\bar{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{y}) = \frac{\ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})\mathbf{1}_B(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\int_B \ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \quad (31)$$

We examine now what happens as $|B| \rightarrow \infty$ (i.e., as the prior becomes more and more diffuse):

- **Inference on $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.** As $|B|$ grows, more and more mass of the likelihood is considered and, with $|B| \rightarrow \infty$, the posterior $\bar{\pi}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{y})$ becomes closer and closer to

$$\bar{\pi}^*(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{y}) = \frac{\ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\int_{\Theta} \ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \frac{\ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})}{S}. \quad (32)$$

This is a proper normalised density and can be used for inference of the vector of interest, $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. The posterior $\bar{\pi}^*(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{y})$ contains only the information provided by the entire likelihood function, and is not affected or distorted by the prior. Note also that, in the limit when $B = \Theta$ if Θ is unbounded, the prior $g(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ becomes equivalent to an improper uniform prior on $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. Hence, a vague/diffuse prior (or a uniform improper prior, which is its limiting case) can be employed for expressing the absence of additional information for inference on $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

- **Model selection.** The Bayes factors are ratio of two marginal likelihoods, that is $\frac{Z_1}{Z_2}$, where each marginal likelihood corresponds to one model that we desire to compare. Two models can differ mainly for the likelihood functions, or for the choice of the prior densities. Therefore, we need to compute the marginal likelihood Z associated to each considered model, i.e.,

$$Z = \int_{\Theta} \ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})g(\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta} = \frac{\int_B \ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta}}{|B|}. \quad (33)$$

Increasing B until covering all parameter space Θ , i.e., $|B| \rightarrow \infty$, and

$$\int_B \ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta} \rightarrow S,$$

and, as a consequence,

$$\lim_{|B| \rightarrow \infty} Z = \lim_{|B| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\int_B \ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta}}{|B|} = 0. \quad (34)$$

Hence, the marginal likelihood of a model with an increasingly diffuse prior tends to zero, so the importance/evidence of the model (with respect to the observed data) also tends to zero. As a consequence, *vague or diffuse priors are highly informative in model selection*: increasingly diffuse priors penalise the model more and more. Hence, the use of vague priors has a clear impact to the results of the model selection [7, 5].

In summary, if $S < \infty$, a good model may yield a low value of Z only because we have chosen a very diffuse prior. On the other hand, a poorer model may yield a larger Z simply because its prior is more concentrated [5, 21, 27, 20]. See, for instance, the example in Appendix B.

5.2 Advice 2: improper priors are forbidden in model selection

In the previous Section, we have shown that diffuse priors are highly informative in model selection. Improper priors can be viewed as limiting cases of diffuse priors. More specifically, assuming unbounded domain Θ , an improper prior is such that

$$\int_{\Theta} g(\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta} = \infty. \quad (35)$$

It is important to remark that the prior $g(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = c \cdot h(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ (where $\int_{\Theta} h(\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta} = \infty$) is not completely specified, since the normalisation constant c does not exist and, as a consequence, this constant is arbitrary. Let us assume that

$$\int_{\Theta} \ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})h(\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta} = D < \infty \quad (36)$$

is finite (in [23] the value D is called *fake evidence*). Computing the Bayesian evidence Z , we get

$$Z = \int_{\Theta} \ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})g(\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta} = c \int_{\Theta} \ell(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta})h(\boldsymbol{\theta})d\boldsymbol{\theta} = c D, \quad (37)$$

i.e., the marginal likelihood Z is also not completely specified due to $c > 0$ is unknown (or arbitrary). Then, improper priors can not be used for computing the marginal likelihood Z , and therefore they are not allowed for model selection unless specific exceptions [23].

6 Conclusions

The accurate modelling of pulsar signals is crucial for applications such as testing general relativity and, in particular, for gravitational waves detection. In this work, we have addressed some possible sources of misinterpretation in the literature related to posterior bias, demonstrating that there exists an underlying identifiability issue in commonly used linear Gaussian pulsar models. A detailed analysis shows that such models are non-identifiable, as infinitely many parameter configurations yield identical likelihoods. While hierarchical priors can serve as a remedy, they effectively impose a specific solution among equally valid alternatives, making the inference highly dependent on prior choice. We have also conducted an empirical analysis of the more sophisticated likelihood function implemented in the state-of-the-art Python package `enterprise`, to assess the presence of a possible non-identifiability issue.

A possible strategy to alleviate this issue could be to partition the available data into multiple subsets or mini-batches, in order to avoid variability over-estimation, and to structure them so that the resulting formulation conforms to a model analogous to Eq. (22), which is identifiable. However, determining an appropriate and theoretically justified strategy for data partitioning remains an open question and should be regarded as an important topic for future research.

Additionally, the work highlights important challenges for Bayesian model selection in pulsar timing array analyses. In particular, the use of diffuse priors, though seemingly uninformative in parameter estimation, can significantly influence model selection outcomes. Improper priors are especially problematic, since they render marginal likelihoods undefined up to arbitrary constants, thereby undermining the validity of Bayes factor-based comparisons.

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References

- [1] G. Agazie, A. Anumalapudi, and A. M. et al. Archibald. The nanograv 15 yr data set: Evidence for a gravitational-wave background. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 951(1):L8, June 2023.

- [2] J. Antoniadis, P. Arumugam, and S. et al. Arumugam. The second data release from the european pulsar timing array: Ii. customised pulsar noise models for spatially correlated gravitational waves. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 678:A49, October 2023.
- [3] G. Ashton and C. Talbot. BILBY-MCMC: an MCMC sampler for gravitational-wave inference. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 507(2):2037–2051, October 2021.
- [4] J. O. Berger and L. R. Pericchi. The intrinsic Bayes factor for model selection and prediction. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 91(433):109–122, 1996.
- [5] J. M. Bernardo and A. F. M. Smith. *Bayesian Theory*. Wiley & sons, 1994.
- [6] C. M Bishop. *Pattern recognition and machine learning*. springer, 2006.
- [7] E. Cameron and A. Pettitt. Recursive pathways to marginal likelihood estimation with prior-sensitivity analysis. *Statistical Science*, 29(3):397–419, 2014.
- [8] J. A. Ellis, X. Siemens, and R. van Haasteren. An efficient approximation to the likelihood for gravitational wave stochastic background detection using pulsar timing data. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 769(1):63, May 2013.
- [9] J. A. Ellis, Mi. Vallisneri, S. R. Taylor, and P. T. Baker. Enterprise: Enhanced numerical toolbox enabling a robust pulsar inference suite, September 2020.
- [10] G. E. Freedman, A. D. Johnson, R. van Haasteren, and S. J. Vigeland. Efficient gravitational wave searches with pulsar timing arrays using Hamiltonian Monte Carlo. *Phys. Rev. D*, 107:043013, 2023.
- [11] B. Goncharov, E. Thrane, R. M. Shannon, J. Harms, N. D. R. Bhat, G. Hobbs, M. Kerr, Richard N. Manchester, D. J. Reardon, C. J. Russell, X.-J. Zhu, and A. Zic. Consistency of the Parkes pulsar timing array signal with a nanohertz gravitational-wave background. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 932(2):L22, jun 2022.
- [12] J. S. Hazboun, J. Simon, X. Siemens, and J. D. Romano. Model dependence of bayesian gravitational-wave background statistics for pulsar timing arrays. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 905(1):L6, December 2020.
- [13] S. Hourihane, P. Meyers, A. Johnson, K. Chatziioannou, and M. Vallisneri. Accurate characterization of the stochastic gravitational-wave background with pulsar timing arrays by likelihood reweighting. *Phys. Rev. D*, 107:084045, Apr 2023.
- [14] A. D. Johnson and et al. Meyers. Nanograv 15-year gravitational-wave background methods. *Physical Review D*, 109(10), May 2024.
- [15] A. D. Johnson, Sarah J. Vigeland, Xavier Siemens, and S. R. Taylor. Gravitational-wave statistics for pulsar timing arrays: Examining bias from using a finite number of pulsars. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 932(2), 2022.

- [16] R. E. Kass and A. E. Raftery. Bayes factors. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 90(430):773–795, 1995.
- [17] N. Laal, S. R. Taylor, R. van Haasteren, W. G. Lamb, and X. Siemens. Solving the pta data analysis problem with a global gibbs scheme. *Physical Review D*, 111(6), 2025.
- [18] L. Lentati, P. Alexander, M. P. Hobson, S. Taylor, J. Gair, S. T. Balan, and R. van Haasteren. Hyper-efficient model-independent bayesian method for the analysis of pulsar timing data. *Phys. Rev. D*, 87:104021, May 2013.
- [19] F. Llorente, L. Martino, E. Curbelo, J. Lopez-Santiago, and D. Delgado. On the safe use of prior densities for Bayesian model selection. *WIREs Computational Statistics*, 15(1):e1595, 2023.
- [20] F. Llorente, L. Martino, D. Delgado, and J. López-Santiago. Marginal likelihood computation for model selection and hypothesis testing: An extensive review. *SIAM Review*, 65(1):3–58, 2023.
- [21] D. J. C. MacKay. *Information theory, inference and learning algorithms*. Cambridge university press, 2003.
- [22] R. Martin, N. Singer, and J. Williams. Valid and efficient possibilistic structure learning in Gaussian linear regression. *arXiv:2511.09305*, 2025.
- [23] L. Martino and F. Llorente. A note on the area under the likelihood and the fake evidence for model selection. *Computational Statistics*, 2025.
- [24] L. Martino and J. Read. A joint introduction to Gaussian Processes and Relevance Vector Machines with connections to Kalman filtering and other kernel smoothers. *Information Fusion*, 74:17–38, Oct 2021.
- [25] A. O’Hagan. Fractional Bayes factors for model comparison. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Methodological)*, 57(1):99–118, 1995.
- [26] D. J. Pascoe, A. Smyrli, T. Van Doorselaere, and A. M. Broomhall. Bayesian Analysis of Quasi-periodic Pulsations in Stellar Flares. *Astrophysical Journal*, 905(1):70, December 2020.
- [27] J. R Oaks, K. A. Cobb, V. N Minin, and A. D. Leaché. Marginal likelihoods in phylogenetics: a review of methods and applications. *Systematic biology*, 68(5):681–697, 2019.
- [28] C. E. Rasmussen. Gaussian Processes in machine learning. In *Summer School on Machine Learning*, pages 63–71. Springer, 2003.
- [29] D. J. Reardon, A. Zic, R. M. Shannon, G. B. Hobbs, and M. et al. Bailes. Search for an isotropic gravitational-wave background with the parkes pulsar timing array. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 951(1):L6, jun 2023.
- [30] C. P. Robert. *The Bayesian choice: a decision-theoretic motivation*. Springer-Verlag, 1994.

- [31] R. van Haasteren. Pulsar timing arrays require hierarchical models. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 273(2):23, jul 2024.
- [32] R. van Haasteren, Y. Levin, P. McDonald, and T. Lu. On measuring the gravitational-wave background using pulsar timing arrays. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 395(2):1005–1014, May 2009.
- [33] I. Verdinelli and L. Wasserman. Computing Bayes factors using a generalization of the Savage-Dickey density ratio. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 90(430):614–618, 1995.
- [34] M. J. Williams, J. Veitch, and C. Messenger. Nested sampling with normalizing flows for gravitational-wave inference. *Phys. Rev. D*, 103:103006, May 2021.
- [35] A. Zic, G. Hobbs, R. M. Shannon, D. Reardon, and B. et al. Goncharov. Evaluating the prevalence of spurious correlations in pulsar timing array data sets. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 516(1):410–420, August 2022.

A Appendix: More accurate estimators for Model A

A.1 Complete likelihood function and frequentist analysis

The likelihood function is

$$\ell(\mathbf{y}_{1:N}|\mathbf{b}_{1:N}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) = p(\mathbf{y}_{1:N}|\mathbf{b}_{1:N}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) = \prod_{n=1}^N \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_n|\mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v). \quad (38)$$

The log-likelihood (up to additive constants) is

$$\log \ell(\mathbf{y}_{1:N}|\mathbf{b}_{1:N}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N (\mathbf{y}_n - \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n)^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v^{-1} (\mathbf{y}_n - \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n) - \frac{N}{2} \log |\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v|. \quad (39)$$

Observe that, in a frequentist approach, \mathbf{b}_n are non-random vectors, hence $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b = \mathbf{0}$ and the variability of \mathbf{y} only depends on $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_y = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v$. The *conditioned maximum likelihood (ML) estimators* are

$$\begin{cases} \widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{ML})} = \widehat{\mathbf{b}}_n(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) = (\mathbf{T}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v^{-1} \mathbf{T})^{-1} \mathbf{T}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v^{-1} \mathbf{y}_n, \\ \widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_v^{(\text{ML})} = \widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_y^{(\text{ML})} = \widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_v(\mathbf{b}_{1:N}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (\mathbf{y}_n - \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n) (\mathbf{y}_n - \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n)^\top. \end{cases} \quad (40)$$

Note that to compute \mathbf{b}_n we need to know $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v$, and to compute $\widehat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}_v$ we need to know all the \mathbf{b}_n 's. Moreover, the equations above are valid if $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b = \mathbf{0}$ (since recall that $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_y = \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v$).

A.2 Marginal likelihood (Bayesian evidence) of all data

Considering the prior $\mathbf{b}_n \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b}|\boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b)$, we can also obtain the marginal distribution of one data \mathbf{y}_n , integrating out \mathbf{b}_n . This is also Gaussian,

$$p(\mathbf{y}_n | \boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) = \int \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_n | \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b}_n | \boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b) d\mathbf{b}_n, \quad (41)$$

$$= \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_n | \boldsymbol{\mu}_s, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v), \quad (42)$$

$$= \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_n | \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v), \quad (43)$$

and we can also write

$$p(\mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_n | \boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) = \prod_{i=1}^N \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_i | \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v + \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top). \quad (44)$$

This is often used for hyperparameter estimation (of $\boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v$) via evidence maximisation [19, 20].

A.3 Posterior distributions of \mathbf{b}_n

The Marginal posterior of each vector \mathbf{b}_n is also Gaussian,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\pi}(\mathbf{b}_n | \mathbf{y}_n, \boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) &= p(\mathbf{b}_n | \mathbf{y}_n, \boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) \propto \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_n | \mathbf{T}\mathbf{b}_n, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b}_n | \boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b) \\ &= \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b}_n | \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{post})}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{post}}), \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{post}} &= (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v^{-1})^{-1} \\ &= (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b^{-1} + \mathbf{T}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v^{-1} \mathbf{T})^{-1} \\ &= \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b \mathbf{T}^\top (\mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v)^{-1} \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b, \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

(the last equality for the Woodbury identity), and the posterior mean

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{post})} &= \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{post}} (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_s^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_s + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v^{-1} \mathbf{y}_n) \\ &= \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{post}} (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b^{-1} \boldsymbol{\mu}_b + \mathbf{T}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v^{-1} \mathbf{y}_n) \\ &= \boldsymbol{\mu}_b + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b \mathbf{T}^\top (\mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b\mathbf{T}^\top + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v)^{-1} (\mathbf{y}_n - \mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\mu}_b). \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

The complete posterior of $\mathbf{b}_{1:N}$ is

$$\bar{\pi}(\mathbf{b}_{1:N} | \mathbf{y}_{1:N}, \boldsymbol{\mu}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_b, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v) = \prod_{n=1}^N \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{b}_n | \hat{\mathbf{b}}_n^{(\text{post})}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{post}}). \quad (48)$$

B Appendix: Illustrative example

In order to clarify the identifiability problem and the consequence of the use of diffuse priors for model selection, we consider a simple univariate linear model with a Gaussian prior over b . This is also a very interesting special case of all the general expressions for the Bayesian regression employed above. Let us consider

$$y_n = b + v_n, \quad n = 1, \dots, N, \quad (49)$$

where $v_n \sim \mathcal{N}(\epsilon|0, \sigma_v^2)$, so that the likelihood of only one observation is

$$p(y_n|b, \sigma_v) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_v^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(y_n - b)^2}{2\sigma_v^2}\right), \quad \text{and} \quad (50)$$

$$g(b) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_b^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(b - \mu_b)^2}{2\sigma_b^2}\right), \quad (51)$$

is the prior over b with hyper-parameters μ_b and σ_b^2 , hence, here $\Sigma_b = \sigma_b^2 \mathbf{I}_N$. Let us now consider N i.i.d. observations y_i and define $\mathbf{y} = [y_1, \dots, y_N]^\top$. The complete likelihood is

$$\ell(\mathbf{y}|b, \sigma_v) = \prod_{i=1}^N p(y_i|b, \sigma_v). \quad (52)$$

In a vectorial form, we can write

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{1}_N b + \mathbf{v}, \quad (53)$$

where $\mathbf{1}_N = [1, \dots, 1]^\top$ is an $N \times 1$ vector of ones. This equation can be rewritten as

$$\underbrace{\mathbf{y}}_{N \times 1} = \underbrace{\mathbf{T}}_{N \times M} \underbrace{\mathbf{b}}_{M \times 1} + \underbrace{\mathbf{v}}_{N \times 1}, \quad (54)$$

and comparing Eqs. (53)-(54), we can see that, in this scenario, $M = 1$ and $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{1}_N$. Hence, the marginal likelihood is

$$Z = p(\mathbf{y}) = p(\mathbf{y}|\sigma_b, \mu_b, \sigma_v) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{0}, \sigma_b^2 \mathbf{1}_N \mathbf{1}_N^\top + \sigma_v^2 \mathbf{I}_N), \quad (55)$$

where $\mathbf{1}_N \mathbf{1}_N^\top$ is an $N \times N$ matrix of 1's in all the entries. This has an important statistical meaning: the observed data y_n 's are *conditional independent* given b , but they are not *independent*. Indeed, we have that $\Sigma_y = \sigma_b^2 \mathbf{1}_N \mathbf{1}_N^\top + \sigma_v^2 \mathbf{I}_N$, hence

$$\begin{aligned} \text{cov}[y_n, y_j] &= \sigma_b^2, \quad \text{for } n \neq j, \\ \text{cov}[y_n, y_n] &= \text{var}(y_n) = \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_v^2. \end{aligned}$$

Namely, the covariance matrix of \mathbf{y} is

$$\Sigma_y = \sigma_b^2 \mathbf{1}_N \mathbf{1}_N^\top + \sigma_v^2 \mathbf{I}_N = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_v^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \dots & \sigma_b^2 \\ \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_v^2 & \dots & \sigma_b^2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \sigma_b^2 & \sigma_b^2 & \dots & \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_v^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (56)$$

Remark. However, without additional information (e.g., another vector \mathbf{y}'), we cannot estimate σ_b , because we have no information about the variability of b .

The log-marginal likelihood (note that here the prior has non-zero mean, i.e., $\mu_b \neq 0$) can be rewritten in this scenario as

$$\log Z = \log p(\mathbf{y}) = -\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_b)^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_y^{-1} (\mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_b) - \frac{1}{2} \log[\det \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_y] - \frac{N}{2} \log(2\pi), \quad (57)$$

where we have defined a $N \times 1$ vector as $\boldsymbol{\mu}_b = [\mu_b, \mu_b, \dots, \mu_b]^\top$. Recall that actually $p(\mathbf{y}) = p(\mathbf{y}|\sigma_b, \mu_b, \sigma_v)$.

Area under the likelihood $S(\mathbf{y}|\sigma_v)$ and improper priors for model selection

If we fix a prior model for b (i.e. we choose σ_b), then the only remaining auxiliary parameter in the observation model (and hence in the likelihood) is σ_v^2 . Clearly, there is also the main variable object of the inference, i.e., b . In a frequentist approach, we could find

$$\left[\hat{b}_{\text{ML}}, \hat{\sigma}_{v\text{ML}} \right] = \arg \max_{b, \sigma_v} \ell(\mathbf{y}|b, \sigma_v). \quad (58)$$

In this specific scenario, we have the analytical expressions of the two estimators in closed form,

$$\hat{b}_{\text{ML}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N y_n, \quad \hat{\sigma}_{\text{ML}}^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (y_n - \hat{b}_{\text{ML}})^2 \approx \sigma_v^2. \quad (59)$$

Note that $\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (y_n - \hat{b}_{\text{ML}})^2$ is a *biased* estimator of the variance σ_v^2 . However, if the area under the likelihood w.r.t. b is finite, in a more Bayesian fashion, we could also study

$$S(\mathbf{y}|\sigma_v) = \int \ell(\mathbf{y}|b, \sigma_v) db. \quad (60)$$

If $S(\mathbf{y}|\sigma_v) < \infty$ for each σ_v , we can maximise this function, for instance. Note that a symmetric approach could be also employed w.r.t. b , i.e., analyzing $S(\mathbf{y}|b) = \int \ell(\mathbf{y}|b, \sigma_v) d\sigma_v$, if finite for each value of b . It is possible to show that maximising $S(\mathbf{y}|\sigma_v)$, we obtain

$$\hat{\sigma}_{\text{S}}^2 = \arg \max_{\sigma_v} S(\mathbf{y}|\sigma_v) = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{n=1}^N (y_n - \hat{b}_{\text{ML}})^2 \approx \sigma_v^2. \quad (61)$$

that is the *unbiased* estimator of the noise variance σ_v^2 . This shows a benefit in integrating out b in (60). Note that this procedure is equivalent to using a uniform improper prior over b , i.e., $g(b) \propto 1$.

Remark. Hence, the use of improper (or diffuse) priors for inference on the parameters is allowed if the area under the likelihood is finite, $S < \infty$. However, diffuse priors are very informative for model selection, see below.

Rewriting the negative log-marginal likelihood,

$$-\log Z = -\log p(\mathbf{y}|\sigma_b) = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_p)^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_y^{-1}(\mathbf{y} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_p)}_{\text{part 1}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}\log[\det \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_y]}_{\text{part 2}} + \text{const.} \quad (62)$$

it is possible to show that, as $\sigma_b \rightarrow \infty$, the first term tends to zero whereas the second term grows to infinity [23]. Hence, we have $-\log Z \rightarrow \infty$ and $Z \rightarrow 0$. As a consequence, diffuse priors are highly informative in model selection (i.e., for computing the marginal likelihood).